

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18009975>

Volume 1 No 1 December (2025): Journal of English Studies

**AN EXPLORATION OF THE AESTHETICS, CONTENT AND POTENTIALS OF
OCCUPATIONAL POETRY AMONG THE HAUSA PEOPLE OF NORTHERN
NIGERIA**

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/7>

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ABSTRACT

This work aims at investigating occupational poetry in Northern Nigeria, specifically focusing on Hausa poetry. The research explored the aesthetic qualities of the various occupational songs and examined how these songs characterise and contribute to promoting the respective occupations. The study adopted both sociological and structuralism critical approaches, which emphasize the social functions of literary works and their reflection of societal needs and values within specific social contexts. Through these lenses, the research explored how the analysed poems reflected the daily experiences, beliefs, and values of the respective occupational groups. The study has provided valuable insights into the diverse occupations and cultural contexts within Nigeria. Through the analysis of four distinct sets of occupational poems representing these professions, the study has achieved its objectives of exploring how the poetry reflects the daily experiences and values of these groups, and reviving interest in these occupations among the youth. This study has deepened our understanding of the occupations in northern Nigeria and the cultural expressions embedded in their poetry.

Keywords: occupational poetry, forms and contents

INTRODUCTION

Oral songs are part of the larger popular culture of the people of Nigerian in general and Hausa people in particular the traditional Hausa Society. Traditional oral poetry comprises performance in form of songs, chants or recitation in which the performer binds himself in advance to follow a certain regular rhythmic pattern. Some oral poetry forms are songs with choric refrains in a call and answer pattern and the songs have alternating sole lines and verses that serve as the chorus or refrains.

In Hausa land, there are songs sung before the Emirs, some to hunters (Mafarauta), professionals (Masu Sanaá), and elite (Masu-Hannu da shuni) for example, songs sung by drumming (jauje) are sung to their relatives. Songs sung by drumming (gangi) are sung by mafarauta/Hunters, while songs sung by drumming (kalangu) are for the community (Jama'a). Singers were known to compose oral traditional songs in Hausa society. Singers were known to compose oral poetry for farmers, hunters, warriors and beggars. In this way, the singers are perceived not only as the embodiment of preserving peoples forms of verbal art, but also of propagating the manner, custom and belief of the people (Abubakar, 64). Oral songs can be defined as an organized performance in which a singer rhythmically sings a song in verses, often accompanied by music and chorus, in other words, songs can be differentiated from mainstream or written poetry, which exists mostly in writing. Oral poetry, the highest and richest art form, is the heart of oral tradition in various parts of Africa. It comes in different forms such as dirges, political songs, religious songs and occupational songs among many others.

Occupation poetry, therefore is a category of verbal art anchored in communities of work. As a form of folk poetry, it often manifests in the everyday settings of jobs and employment. (Sello and

Galane, 12) folklore scholarship and field work has focused on the poetic traditions within a narrow range of occupational roles, including farmers, hunters, warrior and beggars.

Occupational poetry is a form of poetry that reflects the experiences, beliefs, and traditions of people in specific occupations or groups. In northern Nigeria, occupational poetry is an important form of literary expression among hunters, famers, warriors and beggars. These groups of people use poetry to express their daily experiences and concerns, as well as to pass on cultural and social knowledge to future generations.

The forms of occupational poetry in northern Nigeria vary depending on the specific occupation or groups. However, there are common themes and motifs that are shared across the different occupational groups. The poetry is often oral and performed in traditional musical styles, such as the use of drums and other instruments. The language used in the poetry is often a local dialect or a mix of local dialects.

In terms of contents, the poetry of hunters often reflects the importance of hunting in their daily lives, the challenges they face and their connection with nature and the environment. The poetry also illustrates their beliefs, customs, and rituals associated with farming.

Therefore, occupational poetry in northern Nigeria is a form of literary expression that reflects the experiences, beliefs and traditions of hunters, farmers, warriors and beggars. The forms of the poetry are oral and often performed in traditional musical styles, with contents that reflects the daily experiences and concerns of these occupational groups, their connection with nature and the environments, their customs and traditions.

THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

A theory is indispensable to an academic enquiry of this nature because it presents explanatory paradigms that illuminate the subject under consideration. Nicholas Williman defines a theory as “a system of ideas based on interrelated concepts, definitions and propositions with the purpose of explaining or predicting phenomenon” (67). For this study, two theories were adopted due to the nature of the topic and these are sociological criticism and structuralism.

SOCIOLOGICAL CRITICISM

The sociological literary approach has its origin in the studies initiated by early critics such as Plato and Aristotle who investigated the relationship between literature and society and raised pertinent questions about the social implications of literature in the society.

The approach is anchored on the simple conviction that literature is a social product, and thoughts and feelings found in literature are conditioned and shaped by the cultural life created by the society. Even though the foundational work for the approach started right before the eighteenth century, it gained its special place in the history of critical theory in the late twentieth century, through the contributions of Lucien Goldman, Leo Lowenthal, Jonathan Herder, Robert Escarpit and several other social thinkers and critics, each contributing to the development of the approach.

Structuralism is a literary theory which places emphasis on a set of objective criteria for analysis and a new intellectual rigor. Structuralism relied initially on the ideas of the Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure. Like Plato, Saussure regarded the signifier, words, marks and symbols as arbitrary and unrelated to the concept, the signified to which it referred. The scope of semiotics plays an important role in structuralist theory and cultural studies. Semioticians apply structuralist

insights to the study of sign system, a non-linguistic object that can be analyzed as if it were a language (Eagleton, 205).

The structure of a single literary work therefore is determined by how its composition demonstrates the underlying principles of a structural system. Part of the appeal of structuralism says Eagleton, is that like science it reduces complex system to their most fundamental parts. Structuralist's goal is to finding the structures or elements that are common to all cultures, at all times, in all areas of the worlds. From this perspective, the author is cancelled out, since the text is simply the function of a signifying system, not of an individual.

As applied in literary studies, structuralist criticism views literature as a second order signifying system that uses the first-order structural system of language as its medium, and is itself system of language as its medium, and is itself to be analyzed primarily on the model of linguistic theory.

METHODOLOGY

Our sources of data are essentially primary because they exist among the groups of people who are either hunters, farmers, warriors, and beggars. Purposive sampling was used to single these persons out from the rest for the purpose of data collection and secondly, because the data are basically songs, many of them were collected in their original forms as they were sung by the persons concerned. Sometimes, it was necessary to request these persons to sing the songs under controlled environments to be recorded because of the difficulty of capturing the songs in their normal environments. This was especially the case with warriors where it was impossible to get recording from a real war situation. However, with other professionals like beggars, farmers and hunters, they could easily be collected in their original settings, most times without the singers aware that data was being collected.

To collect the songs, recorders on android phones were used in all instances. This was more convenient than having to make arrangements for more elaborated and traditional recording devices for recording not just the audio but the video as well.

For each of these occupations, efforts were made to have at least four songs. This is because a preliminary survey carried out showed that the songs are mostly short in form so targeting at least four per occupation provided enough for research at this level.

DATA ANALYSIS

In the analysis of the songs, attention is focused on the aesthetics, content and potentials of each of them. For each segment of analysis, attempt is made to provide an explanation of the song from the sociological point of view. After this is done, the structures of the songs are carefully examined to identify the structural or technical features of the songs. These technical features, seen to features across all or most of the occupational songs under study, are considered as the aesthetics.

Warrior songs are common among the Hausa people of northern Nigeria and this is not unexpected considering the rich history of violent conflagrations between the Hausas and especially persons considered as infidels. Evidence, therefore, suggests that songs were integral parts of the various campaigns waged by the Hausas against opposing forces to motivate the warriors into valiant acts.

Farmers' songs: Like most ethnic groups in Nigeria, farming is a prized occupation among the Hausa people. They take pride in not only growing what they eat but also using the excess for trade to other parts of Nigeria and even across the border to neighboring Niger Republic.

In terms of structure, this farming song has a very interesting one with the singer reeling out the stanzas while others take the refrains in form of chorus. This gives the songs a group characteristics

and makes it fitting to be used during a farming activity as morale booster with everybody joining in to break the boredom and tiredness that often characterizes farming activity.

Hunters' songs: Just like warriors and farmers, hunters also have their songs among the Hausa people and these are used to edify the profession and build courage among the hunter group while at the sometime attracting the younger ones to the profession. One of such songs is entitled "Waka" which is about Dogozo at Karaye forest. As the song goes, Dogozo was a famous hunter in Gummi Community, he was well known for his fearlessness, during hunt in locations dreaded by other hunters. But here again, the song underscores the importance of hunting, this is because not all people were happy about Dogozo's successes as a hunter. Consequently, some of his peers conspired to eliminate him and what happens is the substance of this song.

Prominent to note in the aesthetics of this song is the presence of a patron. This seems to be characteristic of Hausa occupational songs as there is always a patron whose exploits or otherwise become a rallying point for the other members of profession, inspiring in some cases and deterring in others as can be seen in this particular song. Dogozo commands both sentiments, praise and deterrence. Hunters consider him a role model due to his numerous exploits that became legendary. However, he meets his downfall as a result of his inability to heed a timely warning by friends who ~~are~~ is aware of conspiracy against him.

From the analysis that has been done ~~a book~~, several aesthetic features have emerged as characteristic of occupational poems among the Hausa people of northern Nigeria. First we notice a rich amount of literary devices that perform different functions in each songs. For examples in the warriors songs analyzed, the use of euphemistic expression is prominent. This is mainly because war itself is a deadly happening hence the need to soften the impacts of what is discussed

to make it less disconcerting to the ears. This explains why euphemism, features prominently in war songs.

But apart from euphemism, there is generous use of hyperboles in warriors, farmers, and hunters songs. The intention of these hyperbolic references is to boost the morale of the person involved, boost warriors' egos and make them capable of even more daring actions.

The analysis also reveals generous use of metaphors across all the songs. This is mainly for the purpose of comparison and is found useful where the attributes of certain individuals are compared with related ones for emphasis. Across the songs also can be noticed repetition. This is common in the warriors, hunters and beggars' songs. From the data studied, repetition here serves the purpose of making the songs catchy and easily grasped by many people given that these are expected to be group songs.

Another aesthetic feature found in the occupational songs worthy of note is the use of patrons. All without exception are composed around patrons whose strengths, accomplishments and sometimes weaknesses are used to both encourage and advise members of the occupation. Sometimes weaknesses are used to both encourage and advise members of the occupation as the case may be. Such patrons could be one individual, more than one or groups of persons.

Finally, it has been revealed from the data that Hausa occupational songs are devoid of authorship. This is because, like most oral renditions, they have been around for so long that is hard to say who composed them. In fact the longer, a song lasts, the more varied it becomes with each person or group that sings them injecting fresh flavor into them.

SUMMARY

This work was aimed at investigating occupational poetry in Northern Nigeria, specifically focusing on Hausa poetry. The research explored the aesthetic qualities of the various occupational songs and examined how these songs characterize and contribute to promoting the respective occupations. The study adopted both sociological and structuralist critical approaches, which emphasize the social function of literary works and their reflection of societal needs and values within specific social contexts. Through these lenses, the research explored how the analysed poems reflected the daily experiences, beliefs, and values of the respective occupational groups.

Data Analysis

1. *Dan Bazamfara mai dambe!*

Man from Zamfara, a boxer,

2. *Dan taguwa da saurin girma!*

A young he-camel of rapid growth

3. *Dawan da kututturai, dawan da mala'iku!*

A jungle filled with dangerous stumps!

4. *Dawo Audu ci bayi, mai horo da masaba!*

A jungle with death's angles!

5. *Duna na Sakkwato mai raba gardama!*

Return to us Audu cap!

From the above excerpt, it is clear that occupational poetry is laden with metaphors of different categories. In line two above, the singer praises the boxer by associating him with a foul (young female camel). This representation is intentional as the comparison is ideological; hence it tells opposition groups that the boxer in question has come to a limelight. As such, he will soon defeat his contemporaries or those who have already made name in boxing.

However, in line three of the excerpt above, the singer eulogises the boxer, describes him with powerful nouns and adjectives. The nouns “jungle” and “stumps” are vocatives that allow listeners to reckon the described boxer as big and formidable. This description too meant that the boxer in question has no equal in the nearby villages.

CONCLUSION

The study has provided valuable insight into the diverse occupations and cultural contexts within Nigeria. Through the analysis of four distinct sets of occupational poems representing these professions, the study has achieved its objective of exploring how the poetry reflects the daily experiences and values of these groups, and reviving interest in these occupations among the youth. The poetry of hunters emphasizes their endurance, resilience, and self-reliance in adapting to the challenges of the bush, while also celebrating their connection to nature and the importance of their role in the community. The war songs portrays the realities of war, soldier camaraderie or lack thereof, and the poet's role in motivating and supporting troops.

In conclusion, this study has deepened our understanding of the occupations in northern Nigerian and the cultural expressions embedded in their poetry by exploring the aesthetic content and potentials of occupational poetry, the study has shed light on the values, beliefs and daily experiences of hunters, farmers, warriors and beggars. Furthermore, the study's aim to revive the interest of youths in these occupations, through the propagation of the poetry holds great potentials for preserving cultural heritage.

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